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SOCIO-CULTURAL HERITAGE OF SOUTHERN EUROPE WINE-MAKERS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENOTOURISM (WINE TOURISM)

Abstract. *The article discusses the socio-cultural significance of the winemaking in Southern Europe as a resource for the development of enotourism (wine tourism). The diverse socio-cultural experience of the modern winemakers in the region reflects the connection between past and present, between economy, culture and society. Even in the era of post-globalism, there are opportunities for the preservation and enhancement of tangible and intangible cultural heritage. Natural wine, used for centuries in the Christian church and accompanying the important life events, unites various groups of society, giving the opportunity for harmonious self-realization and socio-cultural tolerance, but only under the condition of constant comprehension: oneself, the national history, and, finally, the cultural and civilizational heritage of different countries. Vineyards and objects of tangible cultural heritage associated with winemaking have received the status of heritage in many countries of Southern Europe, and the culture of winemaking has the state support. National traditions of the winemaking are considered in connection with various types of art – music and fashion, as well as with the effective practices of museum business, advertising and PR. The authors give the examples of interaction between wineries and the museum community and note the successful tourist routes and wine festivals. The authors emphasize the importance of the experience of South European winemaking and enotourism in the creative interaction of traditions and innovations for the southern regions of modern Russia. The long-term practice of outstanding masters of Mediterranean winemaking, based on historical traditions, is an effective marketing strategy.*

The work was supported by YarSU project VIP-018.

Keywords: *winemaking, wine, enotourism, culture, tradition, Southern Europe, Crimea*

Citation: Kozlov, S. A., & Marasanova, V. M. (2022). Socio-cultural heritage of Southern Europe wine-makers for the development of enotourism (wine tourism). *Servis v Rossii i za rubezhom [Services in Russia and Abroad]*, 16(1), 57–65. doi: 10.24412/1995-042X-2022-1-57-65.

Article History

Received 18 January 2022

Accepted 1 March 2022

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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УДК 338.48 EDN: MDMOHR
DOI: 10.24412/1995-042X-2022-1-57-65

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СОЦИОКУЛЬТУРНОЕ НАСЛЕДИЕ ВИНОДЕЛОВ ЮЖНОЙ ЕВРОПЫ В КОНТЕКСТЕ РАЗВИТИЯ ЭНОТУРИЗМА

В статье рассматривается социокультурное значение виноделия Южной Европы как ресурса развития энотуризма. Многообразный социокультурный опыт современных виноделов региона отражает переплетение прошлого с современностью, экономики с культурой и социумом. Даже в условиях эпохи постглобализма имеются возможности для сохранения и преумножения материального и нематериального культурного наследия. Натуральное вино, столетиями используемое в христианском причастии и сопровождающее важные события жизни, объединяет различные группы социума, даря возможность гармоничной самореализации и социокультурной толерантности, но лишь при условии постоянного познания: себя, своей национальной истории, и, наконец, культурно-цивилизационного наследия разных стран. Виноградники и объекты материального наследия, связанные с виноделием, получили в странах Южной Европы статус памятников культуры, а культура употребления вина пользуется государственной поддержкой. Национальные традиции виноделия рассматриваются в связи с различными видами искусства – музыкой и модой, а также эффективными практиками музейного дела, рекламы и пиара. Приведены примеры взаимодействия виноделен с музейным сообществом, отмечены успешные туристские маршруты и винные фестивали. Подчеркивается важность опыта южноевропейского виноделия и энотуризма, включая творческое взаимодействие традиций и новаций, для южных регионов современной России. Многолетняя практика выдающихся подвижников средиземноморского виноделия, основанная на верности традициям, одновременно является эффективной маркетинговой стратегией.

Работа выполнена при поддержке проекта ЯрГУ VIP-018.

Ключевые слова: виноделие, вино, энотуризм, традиции, Южная Европа, Крым

Для цитирования: Козлов С.А., Марасанова В.М. Социокультурное наследие виноделов Южной Европы в контексте развития энотуризма // Сервис в России и за рубежом. 2022. Т.16. №1. С. 57–65. DOI: 10.24412/1995-042X-2022-1-57-65.

Дата поступления в редакцию: 18 января 2022 г.

Дата утверждения в печать: 1 марта 2022 г.

The research problem. The wine became a global economic and socio-cultural phenomenon, it is a marker of the globalization. At the same time the availability and attractiveness of wine represent the virtues of the bourgeois lifestyle in general and its wine symbols in particular, including such "superpowers" in the field of winemaking as France and Italy. In the perception of the high-quality wine by the modern mass consumer the accents are clearly shifting from the physiological and gastronomic dominants of aroma and taste (which prevailed 15-20 years ago) to the social and cultural aspects. In the taste analysis of one of the key elements of the characteristics of the wine – the proportions of tannin and acidity – are increasingly used (by the consumers and by the advertisers) not only linguistic comparisons based on physiology and emotion, but also a much wider range of assessments, including sociocultural, psychological and even historical associations. At the same time, wine is sometimes compared with the qualities of a person, which is a feature of the wine metaphor in the modern advertising tourism narrative [11, p. 163]. This trend indicates the noticeable increase of the cultural demands of the modern consumer and shows the changing of the very nature of the winemaking: its intellectual and "spiritual-cathartic" functions expanded. Wine and winemaking become an incentive and the basis of tourism, increasing the range of tourist offers for different regions and countries.

Socio-cultural aspects of the winemaking are so important as economic issues: a highly developed culture of winemaking is one of the important elements of the axiological value system in the mentality of the nation, an indicator of its viability and strength. It is no coincidence that a modern winery is, as a rule, a multifunctional economic and cultural complex, in which, along with profitability, a huge place is given to education and wine culture spreading: thus, winemaking embodies the sociocultural and metaphysical symbolism of Tradition.

Region of study. Southern Mediterranean, where winemaking has been known since the 2nd millennium BC, became the "cradle" of many

socio-cultural traditions and practices, and wine is one of the key cultural symbols of the region. Wine is an important part of the Christian culture and the European civilization. Sociocultural aspects of the winemaking are embodied in the customs and mentality of the peoples of Southern Europe – Italians, Spaniards, Portuguese, Greeks, Cypriots, etc., as well as in gastronomy, politics, literature (enogastronomic genre) and other areas of life, including even medicine (wine therapy). A significant part of the world's wines is produced in Southern Europe; large-scale wine festivals and wine tours are held here. Local wineries became a well-deserved pride of the region, showing not only its history and culture, but also modern achievements.

It is no coincidence that the ancient vineyards, wine presses and cellars for storing wine in the countries of Southern Europe have the status of cultural monuments, and the culture of wine has universal respect and state support. The diverse socio-cultural experience of the modern winemakers in the region reflected the interweaving of the past with the present, the economy with culture and society. Outstanding wines created by Mediterranean winemakers (primarily Italian and Spanish) are the products of the Earth, the result of labor and a piece of art – a powerful accumulator of life energy and a healing source of inspiration and at the same time a significant contribution to the world culture heritage. In the situation of rapid climate change and the aggravated ecological situation, the small islands of the winemaking remain centers of stability and heritage preservation, testifying to the possibility of the sustainable development of the local traditions in the period of the globalization.

On the example of the winemaking in Southern Europe we can see a conscious return to the Tradition, to a careful and respectful attitude towards the mighty elements of the Nature, previously tamed and suppressed by the technogenic civilization of the 20th century. At the same time, the axiology of the soul changes: the proximity to the Earth, the rejection of strict market requirements aimed at the mass consumer and

maximum profit, a creative synthesis of the traditions and innovations make it possible to preserve the best human qualities: diligence, kindness, responsiveness, etc. All the above circumstances contribute to the development of enotourism (wine tourism) in Southern Europe and allow to extend the successful practices to the other regions and countries.

Previous researches. The history of winemaking, the oldest branch of agriculture, has already been reflected in the scientific literature [3, 19, 20]. It is important for practical application to analyze the rich socio-cultural experience of modern innovative winemakers of Southern Europe as the basis for productive business strategies and effective advertising campaigns, as well as for territorial branding and enotourism [1, 7, 13, 15, 17]. The experience of the winemaking and enotourism in Southern Europe is especially useful for the Crimea [14, 16] and has great perspectives. As was noted by an outstanding Italian oenologist Giacomo Takis, wine has no crisis: people have always drunk it and will drink, seeking to find comfort, joy and hope [17, 13].

National winemaking traditions as the basis of enotourism in Southern Europe. Italy holds a special position in the modern winemaking. The ancient Greeks called its southwestern region Enotria ("a country rich in vineyards"). The unique variety of the climatic zones allows to produce a wide range of grape varieties and wines. Every Italian region has its own distinctive social and cultural wine-making traditions but, first of all, we should single out Tuscany where the connection between the traditional and present can be traced especially clear. The concept of "wine", which first became an object of study during the Renaissance period, occupies a huge place in the mentality of the Tuscans embodying their native land – its history, love, labour and beauty.

For example, Josko Gravner, a winemaker from the Italian province of Friuli Venezia Giulia, makes white wines of the highest quality including Pinot Grigio. The winemaking experience of Georgia is used here: the wine is aged for at least six months in kvevri clay jugs (in 2013 this

production method was included in the UNESCO List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity: the oldest kvevri was found on the ruins of the Dangreuli Gora settlement in the Central Georgia and dates back to the 7th millennium BC) and then for the other two and a half years in oak barrels. According to Josko Gravner, wine is a product of nature, not a human; grapes retain their genetic code and give natural, fine, ecological wine [15].

In some wineries the grapes are pressed with the feet as in the old days (Sicilian Dos Tueras of Badalucco de la Iglesia Garcia). Following the traditions results in the production of the high-quality wine. In 2018 La Vigna di Milano wine was produced in the revived vineyard in Milan donated in 1499 for the painting of The Last Supper by Leonardo da Vinci and now turning into an open-air museum. The beauty of nature made it possible to evaluate the local wines and nature as "inspiring resources" [5, p. 245-248], contributed to the popularity of the Italian wines, and the magnificent red wines of Tuscany took one of the leading positions in the world wine "Table of ranks" [7].

Social and cultural traditions are honoured by winemakers in Spain, a country where wine is an essential part of both lifestyle and national mentality. At the same time in the collective consciousness of Spaniards the culture of wine consumption is strongly associated with a healthy life. Moderate doses of immune-boosting dry red wine are an important element of the therapeutic Mediterranean diet included in the UNESCO List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity in 2010.

In Portugal wine-making traditions are supported by law: regional wines must be made from about 250 local grape varieties. Most Portuguese winemakers use original old methods, such as squeezing the juice from the grapes with the feet and aging the wine in the oak barrels. But, perhaps, the main social and cultural achievement of this country in the field of winemaking is a highly developed (even in comparison with Italy and Spain) enotourism. Let's single out the Alianca

company founded in 1927. José Berardo, the controlling shareholder and art connoisseur, created the Lisbon Museum of Contemporary Art. Cultural events are organically included in the programs of the popular wine tourist routes. In the cellars of the Bairrada region winery the history of the winemaking is organically combined with the demonstration of the unique collections: Zimbabwean modern art, one of the world's largest collections of minerals, collections of furniture and ceramics, etc. Other Portuguese wine tours, including a visit to the XV century wine estate of Quinta dos Liridos in the Obidos region (also owned by José Berardo), the unique and largest in Europe *Buddha Eden* oriental park (about 35 ha) created in protest against the barbaric destruction of the Buddhas of Bamiyan by the Taliban in Afghanistan (2001) are equally interesting. Here tourists can get acquainted with the modern sculptures of the Berardo Museum and other attractions [12].

Winemaking, Music, Fashion. The South European winemaking and modern musical culture have diverse connections: music and wine both can inspire and support a person, including them into society and at the same time acting as the most important context of catharsis, as well as the polyphony of Creativity. Let's single out Sensation – a series of Italian sparkling wines, created in honor of the famous club music festival of the same name. And, for example, under the patronage of the Cyprus Wine Museum (near Limassol), opened in 2000, not only excursions to local wineries, but also classical music concerts are regularly organized.

Music plays an important role in the modern wine trade. At the same time, an interesting pattern was revealed: the sound of music of high tones more often contributes to the choice of white wines, and heavy basses and baritones, on the contrary, red wines (Chianti, Barolo, Amarone, etc.), which, first of all, Southern Europe is famous for. The analogies with music, in our opinion, are obvious: from the low register of the Red (meditative-spiritual Enlightenment) – the return again to the White (embodying the joys and

sorrows of human Being). The popularity of sparkling wines (prosecco, etc.) grows, which is often associated with the atmosphere of the holiday – music of the soul. Not surprisingly, Italian wineries are most often owned by musicians and singers: Andrea Bocelli (whose family acquired a vineyard in Tuscany in 1840), Albano Carrisi (owner of 65 hectares of vineyards producing 350,000 bottles of wine annually), Sting (who gave the names of his songs to the wines).

Large-scale wine festivals in the countries of Southern Europe can be noted, for example, Calici di Stelle is the largest wine festival of the summer, taking place from August 4 to 10 throughout Italy. Famous wine holidays are the Chianti wine festivals in Tuscany, the sherry festival in Spain, the Cypriot wine festival in Limassol, World Lambrusco Day (June 20), International Albariño Days (August 1-5). These and other similar events, which have rightfully proven themselves to be "celebration of life" and a living embodiment of people's gratitude for the fertility of the earth (which is especially important in the context of the general impoverishment of nature under the pressure of modern technology), make a significant contribution to introducing people to the wine culture, and at the same time and in the preservation of the national traditions of work and life.

Winemaking is closely connected with modern fashion industry [see also: 6], embodying luxury, hedonism, and sometimes outrageousness along with its originality. The demand for trendy wines is rapidly growing, meeting two main criteria – to be in trend and at the same time fully and vividly reflect the unique individuality of a person, their image and original taste. At the same time not only the previously established factors (aroma, taste and cost of wine) are defining, but also obtaining information about the history of the drink (general and regional, as well as a specific winery), the features of its production and perception. The implementation of these tasks most optimally meet the wines from the local grape varieties. For example, noble white wines are rapidly gaining popularity in Spain: albariño,

gordelho (Galicia) and ondarrabi (Catalonia); in Italy – the wines of Friuli, Lombardy, Trentino-Alto Adige.

Advertising and PR in winemaking. Among the marketing strategies of the Mediterranean wineries we can highlight the creation of a direct valorization of the area image and reputation including the use of the winery's architectural image in the graphic design of its products which helps to achieve the maximum integration of a particular winery into the surrounding landscape. This is typical for the famous Italian Antinori Winery [1, p. 164-165]. In some cases the wineries' architectural structures are the outstanding pieces of modern art (Italian wineries of Antinorinel Chianti Classico in Bargino and Petra Winery in Suvereto, Spanish farms of Marqués de Riscal in Elciego (with a pink titanium facade of the building "flowing" like a ribbon, built within the City of Wine project) and Bodegas Portia in Ribera del Duero, Portuguese winery of L'And Vineyards in Montemor-o-Novo) often referring the consumer to the historical and cultural tradition.

So the name of the Spanish winery "Bodegas Ysios" in Rioja is a direct reference to the Egyptian gods Osiris and Isis, closely associated with the winemaking. The cultural symbols are skillfully interpreted here: for instance, the triangular structure of the R. López de Heredia winery in Rioja, built in 2006, symbolizes the bridge between the past, present and future of this world-famous winery. Such farms, often with a cult status, are man-made islands of natural harmony, calm and relaxation which is extremely important in our time saturated with all sorts of information (often negative).

It is noteworthy that the various Mediterranean winemakers actively use naming tools in their advertising campaigns: for instance, the name of the wine "I don't care" reminiscent of the value of serenity was created in Central Greece [14, p. 58]. Print advertising, often approaching to the piece of art with its quality, is largely based on science and skillfully applies the physiology, psychology and spiritual needs of a person [18].

The reliance on traditions has found a vivid

reflection in advertising campaigns of the Italian wine brands. At the same time, advertising transfers social and cultural experience. Let us single out the advertisement of the Botter winery, founded in 1928, focuses on the feeling, passion as well as on devotion to labour peculiar to the line of Apulian Gran Passione wines which sacredly honours traditions of the land. The advertisement emphasizes patriotism specific for the members of this family company: in their opinion, being Italian is a style of life, thinking, creativity, food, drinking and being. It is no coincidence that the winery strongly supports the #P2BI hashtag which means the pride of being a local resident.

The practice of promoting advertising and PR texts in Italian winemaking has a positive effect on communication in this area. At the same time, the social and cognitive functions of advertising are expanding: its axiological tasks closely related to the development of the individual and society come to the fore. It is typical that advertising of wine products practically does not use such an effective but politically incorrect method as the use of fears and weaknesses of the consumer. On the contrary, the advertising emphasizes the positive things. At the same time, the advertising campaigns of the individual winemakers of the region are sometimes severely criticized due to the plots unacceptable for various reasons: for instance, analysts noted the Simon Wiesenthal Center's call for a boycott of the Italian company selling Vini Lunardelli products since its labels not only depicted photographs of the fascist leaders but displayed Nazi and fascist slogans [14, p. 59].

As for the elite bourgeois environment of Europe and the world, for many years it has maintained a strong commitment to the great Italian wines of Tuscany and Piedmont primarily to wines from Nebbiolo (Barolo and Barbaresco) and Sangiovese (Chianti) grapes shrouded in magic of medieval history and culture. Let us single out the Amarone wines, red and white Recioto (white sweet wine "Recioto di Soave" was the favorite wine of Dante Alighieri, Frank Sinatra and Federico Fellini). Thus, the southern wine also acts as a symbol of luxury, success in life, an attribute of PR.

Let us note the wine snobbery which is widespread in the European countries and the USA [2]: there is a strong opinion that the ability to understand wines is an indicator of high status and intellectual development. This phenomenon is also emerging in modern Russia where the number of VIP winemakers is also growing every year and the collecting of wine labels and wine (as a tool for long-term investment) is developing. However, the wine snobbery is not typical for Southern Europe: this is hindered by the high level of the everyday wine culture. Besides, professional winemakers who enjoy their authority in the society harshly criticize the wine snobs.

Significance of the experience of the South European winemakers for Russia. The unique experience of the South European winemaking, including the creative interaction of traditions and innovations, begins to spread in the southern regions of modern Russia, the conditions of which are more favorable for the development of this important agricultural industry in comparison with other regions. In addition it is in the Northern Black Sea region that viticulture and winemaking have old historical roots from the 2nd century BC.

The heritage and traditions of the Apennine winemakers are successfully used in the farms of the Crimea – a region historically and culturally closely connected with Italy [16], in which the development of winemaking received a powerful impulse at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries [8; 14]. The typical example is the Sevastopol plant Zolotaya Balka agricultural firm, which has modern Italian equipment. There is a tourist complex on the territory of the plant. In 2018 the first joint Italian-Crimean wine project was launched by famous winemakers Valery Zakharin and Ettore Falvo. In addition, the #WineFest Harvest and Wine Festival is held annually in Crimea (organized by Zolotaya Balka); a variety of wine tours, exclusive vineyard tours. In 2018 the circular wine and gastronomic tourist route Wine Road of Crimea with a total length of 480 km united 15 wineries and wine and cognac factories, hotels and farms. Agrotourism and wine therapy are actively developing here, they are accompanied by seeing

of historical monuments and natural locations and visits to museums. All this gives great opportunities to using the richest experience of wine tourism in the Mediterranean [4]. During 2020 tourist season about half a million people visited the tasting rooms of Crimean wineries. Let us single out such popular tourist projects as Wine Roads of Kuban (an initiative of Abrau-Dyurso, which also operates the Museum of Ancient Winemaking) and Wine Roads of the Bosphorus Kingdom.

However, in Russia both the "wine culture" and enotourism associated with that type of culture enotourism are just emerging. Only in the 18th century the concept of "wine" was included in Russian literature and poetry, and the concept of "culture of drinking" appeared. Even at the early 1900s writer and philosopher Vasily Vasilyevich Rozanov, who traveled around Italy, bitterly noted that the habitual drunkenness as a «national vice» takes away history from the Russian people [5, p. 262]. Economic, legal, national, and cultural aspects closely intertwined in the production and the consumption of the alcohol [10]. Until now, Russians, knowing that they need to drink dry red wine at room temperature, lose sight of the fact that this tradition referred to the temperature of the rooms of medieval castles (15-16° C), not modern apartments.

Gorbachev's anti-alcohol campaigns of the late 1900s dealt a crushing blow to the wine culture of our country [9]. It takes at least 7-8 years for a winemaker to give a birth to his wine, and only a few enthusiasts are ready to show patience, hard work, willpower and faith in ultimate success, realizing that market requests can change very quickly.

We point out the large-scale project Wine Roads ("Iter Vitis – Les Chemins de la Vigne") as a European cultural route promoting both continental gastronomic tourism and the cultural heritage of specific wine-growing regions. In 2017 a Memorandum was signed on the establishment of the program "Iter Vitis – Russia", the main tasks of which are not only the wide promotion of the cultural heritage of the South Russian wine-

growing regions, but also the creation of a network of wine and gastronomic cultural routes. Italy in this case acts as a model (reference sample), because there is a well-functioning chain of enoroutes – wine tours with degustations.

Conclusions. The creative experience of the modern winemakers in the Southern Europe shows that even in the conditions of the post-globalism, there are opportunities for the preservation and enhancement of tangible and intangible cultural heritage. Natural wine, used for centuries in Christian church and accompanying the important life events, unites various groups of society, giving the opportunity for harmonious self-realization and sociocultural tolerance, but only under the condition of constant knowledge: oneself, the national history, and, finally, the cultural and civilizational heritage of different countries. It can be admitted that Creativity brightly and multifaceted acts in winemaking as an integral element of the socio-cultural landscape of Being even in the conditions of the expected unification of modern economic life. Thus, it is possible to

partially overcome the egoism of the modern market alienating a person from society, and passionaries receive the rich food for thought: about the fate of man, nature and society; about the importance of the synthesis of spiritual and rational principles; about the experience of the Past – and the hope for Renewal.

Perhaps the main message of the Mediterranean winemakers can be formulated as follows: Freedom and Happiness – in the difficulties, joy and inspiration of Creativity, the polyphony of a personally responsible Choice, adapted to Nature and fidelity to Tradition. Today, the richest socio-cultural heritage of winemakers develops. This experience, based on family and professional traditions, in the early 2000s became a reliable basis not only for branding user preferences, but also implemented in effective advertising campaigns and in the development of the enotourism. The long-term practice of outstanding masters of Mediterranean winemaking, based on historical traditions, is an effective marketing strategy.

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